

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

REFERENTIAL CONFLICTS IN ENGLISH NEWSPAPER TEXTS

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Abstract

The paper establishes the types of referential conflicts and their linguistic means in the result of the analysis of the encoding methods of the subject components in reference structures of English newspaper texts by the methods of semantic and contextual analysis. The paper defines structural (the difference in the grammatical number of the antecedent and anaphor), contextual-semantic (several activated hyponyms correlated with one hypernym) and culturally specific reasons for the occurrence of referential conflicts in English newspaper texts. The methods for resolving referential ambiguity with the help of deep-semantic and extralinguistic factors are determined. The genre specificity of referential conflicts that prevail in English interviews is revealed.

Keywords: referential conflict, subject reference, full and reduced referential expression, anaphor, antecedent.

Introduction

The study of issues related to subject reference in (de)authorization structures of newspaper texts seems relevant, because it directly affects the quality and verifiability of information in mass media, relates to information management and can trigger various socio-cultural and legal processes, and therefore is of interest both to modern humanitarian science and to society as a whole. Subject reference, which identifies the subjects – sources of information mentioned in the text (its fragment) and can be explicated by any parts of speech, the use of which is possible as part of the nominative core [Vlasenko 2010: 118], continues to attract the attention of scholars and directs their research efforts in areas that have not been fully explored. Such areas include issues connected with the reasons, linguistic means of referential conflicts in a media text and potential ways of resolving them. The material for this paper consists of English newspaper texts of different genres: 60 news texts, 20 opinion texts, and 20 interviews (transcripts).

Subject reference has two methods of linguistic marking: a) full, which is carried out with the help of proper and common nouns; b) reduced, realized with the help of pronouns and null subjects (third-person zeros, or implied subjects) [Budyonnaya 2018: 14-16]. In the text, to encode the same subject, the author can simultaneously use full and reduced referential expressions, between which anaphoric relations are established. A referential expression that refers to another, used earlier, is called an anaphor, and the one preceding it is called an antecedent [Yurchenko 2017: 7]. If the coreference of subject nominations is established by the addressee unambiguously, then recognizing anaphoric connections is not difficult, which, however, is not always the case in speech. There are cases of referential ambiguity in texts, when it may turn out that an anaphoric means (for example, a pronoun) is potentially related to two (or more) antecedents in the text, for example: *My little sister really liked her new teacher. She always came to class ten minutes before the bell* (example by A.N. Yurchenko). In the case of such ambiguity,

referential conflict arises, i.e. a situation in which, within the current discourse fragment, the addressee can attribute the referential means used by the speaker to several referents activated in his working memory [Fedorova, Uspenskaya 2010]. It should be noted that referential conflict created by pronouns is the most studied in modern linguistics, while other referential expressions that have the property of referential ambiguity have received fragmentary attention.

Linguists divide referential conflicts into temporary ones, in relation to which the conflict is resolved as the entire text is read, for example, using the strategy of “searching for referents and eliminating competition” [Glazkov 2024: 265], and permanent ones, for which the conflict is not resolved, and the addressee has to make a choice between two possible referents. In any case, the reader must do additional mental work to correlate what is said in a given fragment with what was in the text earlier and only then interpret the information [Guseva 2017: 97]. According to researchers, if there are conditions for the emergence of referential conflict (for example, the text talks about characters of the same sex who can be named by the same pronoun), the substituting pronoun should not be used, since it can complicate the process of reference for the reader and cause the reader to misunderstand which character is performing a particular action [ibid]. Pronominals are especially undesirable when there is a change in points of view, therefore, often in a text, especially a media text, with a frequent change of speaking subjects introducing a new text fragment, the use of full referential expressions is required to avoid referential conflict [Guseva 2017: 100].

My analysis of newspaper texts of different genres in English has shown that all referential types of subjects (definite, generalized, and indefinite), encoded by full nominal groups at the initial mentioning and by reduced referential expressions at the repeated references, as a rule, are unambiguously related to antecedents due to anaphoric connections and do not create conditions for referential conflict, which is typical for

both 1) pronominal use and 2) third-person zeros. Thus, anaphoric pronouns, as a rule, do not allow an alternative in identification and encode maximally activated referents mentioned in the previous context, by which it is easy to identify a full referential expression marking the antecedent: *But Israeli prime minister Benjamin Netanyahu has stressed any truce deal would delay, not prevent, a ground invasion of Rafah...; "I've set three war goals...", he said, speaking on CBS* (The Guardian, 27.02.2024).

In the case of reduced referential expressions with third-person zeros, the previous context also often allows to relate them to their antecedents: *In the unmarked villas, private dining rooms and scholarly retreats where well-connected Chinese sometimes offer opinions to foreigners, Mr Trump is called ignorant, erratic and tiresome, but not without his uses. He is praised for an apparent indifference to ideology. He is complimented for his reluctance to condemn Chinese repression in such places as Xinjiang* (The Economist, 11.06.2020).

The implied subjects of speech for the structures *is called, is praised, is complimented* are related to the non-referential generalized subject *well-connected Chinese* used in the first part of the first sentence, therefore the referential choice of reduced means does not lead to referential conflict. Nevertheless, we note that in media texts the implied subject cannot always be inferentially derived through the context, and even if a contextual contender for the eliminated subject is subsequently discovered, the reader's efforts to establish referential connections may lead the addressee into the interpretive sphere and not coincide with the journalistic intention of encoding.

Sometimes, however, in modern media texts it is not possible to avoid the emergence of referential conflict when using reduced referential means in the form of pronouns. Despite the fact that the referential conflict filter prohibits the use of a pronoun in the presence of more than one potential referent, such cases are still occasionally encountered in media texts, and anaphoric connections, close linear-textual arrangement and internal properties of the referent (for example, referential definiteness) do not contribute to its resolution: *The four Children's Commissioners for the UK have published a joint letter calling for this, and in a letter to this newspaper 15 former presidents of the Oxford University Students Union have urged the institution to do the same. They added that pressing ahead with plans to award GCSEs results on Thursday based on the algorithm would be "suicide". The Government were understood to be furious that the advice appeared to undermine their promise of a 'triple lock' on results* (The Telegraph, 17 August, 2020). Here the first sentence of the text presents two activated referents in plural, *the four Children's Commissioners for the UK and 15 former presidents of the Oxford University Students Union*, coded by full referential expressions. In the utterance that follows, the antecedent is coded by the anaphoric pronoun *they*, which offers a referential alternative in the choice of the two activated referents. As for the sentence with the third-person zero *were understood*, the referential alternative here is broader than

that of the anaphoric pronoun, since the implied subject can be not only the two linguistically coded referents in the previous context, but also an unlimited number of people. If the subject-referential alternative is preserved in the media text, referential conflict is unresolved.

Cases of unresolved subject-referential conflict in English newspaper texts are created not only by the anaphoric, but also by the personal pronoun *we* in a generalized-collective meaning, which does not correlate with textual antecedents equivalent to "I + specific subject(s)". Let us compare the contexts from the interview with the journalist Julian Assange: *One of the unintended consequences is the opposite effect, which is what we've seen with the Department of Defense. I saw this problem early on in our first year, that the analytical effort which we thought would be supplied by Internet citizens around the world was not, I saw that, well, actually, in terms of articles, form tends to follow the funding. However, we do know that the FBI has been going around Boston visiting number of people there...* (Time, 1.12.2010).

In addition to cases with pronominal means, for which it is not possible to establish anaphoric connections unambiguously, referential conflict in media texts can be created by the semantics of linguistic units of non-pronominal status. Such cases are recorded in the presence of hyper-hyponymous relations in the nominative series of activated referents and the replacement of one of them in the subsequent context by a generic word that can be related simultaneously to both nominations, for example: *American President Joe Biden has agreed to allow Ukraine to strike targets ... under certain conditions, said American official, according to Agence France-Presse. "The president has tasked his team..." the source said* (Daily News, 23.07.2024).

Referential conflict in media texts can also be created by specific non-nominal markers with the implied presence of the subject of speech. Thus, in English media culture, in information and analytical genres, there is a specific marker *reportedly*, in relation to which the conditions for referential conflict exist due to its referential ambiguity and are determined by the semantics of the unit itself 'according to what some people say' [Oxford Learners Dictionary], which can complicate the process of reference for the reader and cause the addressee to misunderstand who exactly is communicating the information. For this marker, within the text, the range of potential referents is often blurred: it is difficult to determine whether this means is an element of the nominative series associated with other mentioned sources of information in the media text, representing a nominative variation in order to avoid repetitions when referring to sources, or whether its referential scope is wider and relates to the media in general. Let us consider the following media fragment: *Hamas was considering a draft agreement for a 40-day pause in fighting, according to a Reuters source... The draft also reportedly stated Hamas would free 40 Israeli hostages... A deal could include the release of several hundred Palestinian detainees held by Israel, media reports suggest* (The Guardian, 27.02.2024).

When decoding a referentially ambiguous marker, the implied subject signaled by the reduced referential expression *reportedly* is most likely related to a certain Reuters source and is used for the purposes of nominative variation. In any case, the inclusion of referentially ambiguous expressions in media texts not only hinders the identification of the subject, but also creates conditions for referential conflict. Along with unresolved referential conflict, English media culture demonstrates cases – albeit quite rare – of referential conflict that is resolved in the media text by additional means or contextually. Compare: **Another civil servant who worked in one of Raab's departments said they had seen him "behave quite aggressively towards officials". They added that the government's claim that there had been no "formal" complaints against Raab was telling** (The Times, 15.11.2022).

Taking into account the text categories of coherence and cohesion and as a result of applying the retrospective strategy of text decoding when searching for candidates for the anaphoric pronoun *they*, referential conflict is resolved, despite the fact that they are not located in immediate linear-textual proximity. In the statement: *One official said: "He would become angry with no justification"* (The Times, 15.11.2022) the antecedent *one official* is mentioned, which, together with *another civil servant who worked in one of Raab's departments*, is correlated with the anaphor *they*.

Sometimes the emergence of referential conflict in media texts is facilitated by the discrepancy in the grammatical number of the antecedent and anaphor, and its resolution is influenced by deep-semantic factors. Consider the following context: *We have been contacted by the State Department. They do not believe that there are many people that would be vulnerable* (Time, 1.12.2010). Pronominal substitution of an official body with a change in grammatical number is typical of English media culture: for example, the subjects *Ofqual, the regulator* and *they* act as co-referents, as well as other collective nouns such as *the police, the board*, etc. can be replaced by the plural pronoun *they*, meaning their members. The results of the quantitative analysis allow to assert that in media texts in English, in the overwhelming majority of cases, the situation of referential conflict does not arise, while an interesting genre specificity is recorded. Thus, in essays referential conflict was not detected, in news and opinion articles it is rare, is found in 5% of texts and is caused by the activation of several referents simultaneously. It is interesting that in interviews the share of texts with referential conflict is significant: 50%, which is due to both the simultaneous activation of several referents and the use of the pronoun *we* by the interviewee in the generalized-collective meaning, which does not correlate with the text antecedents. Let us demonstrate what has been said using Diagram 1.

Diagram 1.

Conclusion

In English newspaper texts of different genres, the choice of a referential means of encoding information sources by a journalist with a combination of different referential means in most cases does not allow for an alternative interpretation by the reader and does not lead to referential conflict. In rare cases, in English news and opinion articles, reduced referential expressions with anaphoric pronouns or third-person zeros create a referential alternative in the form of two (or more) full noun phrases and lead to referential conflict regardless of the type of subject reference. A significant share of texts with referential conflict in English interviews is explained by the simultaneous activation of several referents and the use by the speaker (interviewee) of the pronoun *we* in the generalized collective meaning. In English newspaper texts, referential conflict is usually resolved by additional means or contextually. Cases of unresolved referential conflict are recorded when the subject-referential alternative is preserved throughout the newspaper text.

The basis for the emergence of referential conflict in media texts may lie in the discrepancy in the grammatical number of the antecedent and the anaphoric pronoun, and the method of its resolution is deep-semantic factors. The referent representing an official body, verbalized by the full referential expression and presented by noun in singular, when using the reduced referential expression can be encoded by the anaphoric pronoun in plural, thereby marking not so much the institution itself as its representatives. Units of non-pronominal status can create referential conflict in the presence of several activated referents encoded by hyponymous units, and the replacement of one of them in the text with a hypernym, which can simultaneously correlate with several activated hyponyms. A specific non-pronominal means capable of creating the preconditions for the emergence of referential conflict in English media texts due to referential ambiguity is the marker *reportedly*.

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